

Supply Chain Planning and Performance of Road Transport Sector Agencies in Kenya.

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ABSTRACT

The transportation landscape differs significantly between developed countries and Africa, particularly Kenya, where road transport dominates. Despite the importance of road infrastructure for economic progress, Kenya's road network faces challenges in achieving optimal performance. This study investigates the relationship between supply chain planning and the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya, with insights drawn from various sources including the African Development Bank, European Union, National Treasury, and Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure. The study aimed to establish the influence of supply chain planning on agency performance, focusing on key agencies responsible for road network facilitation, namely KeNHA, KURA, and KeRRA. It addressed the need for enhanced market access and the challenges hindering the realization of efficient road networks despite substantial resource allocations. A cross-sectional study spanning 12 months was conducted, utilized a positivist approach to collect objective data. A sample size of 254 personnel from the three agencies is selected using stratified random sampling, and data is collected through structured questionnaires and secondary sources. Statistical analysis, including correlation analysis and regression models, is employed to evaluate the relationships between variables. The study findings reveal a strong and statistically significant relationship between supply chain planning and agency performance, with descriptive statistics indicating positive perceptions of supply chain planning among respondents. The recommendations include prioritizing the development and implementation of comprehensive supply chain plans, investing in training programs for personnel, and fostering stakeholder collaboration. Areas for further research are identified, including comparative studies across sectors and regions, longitudinal investigations into the long-term effects of supply chain planning, and qualitative exploration of factors influencing planning effectiveness. In conclusion, this study contributes to understanding the dynamics of supply chain planning within the road transport sector in Kenya, offering insights to inform policy and practice in infrastructure development and procurement management.

Keywords: *Supply Chain Planning, Performance of Road Transport Sector Agencies*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The world's population has surpassed 8 billion, putting pressure on resources and leading to the implementation of protectionist policies (Population Reference Bureau, 2022; World Bank, 2022; Garver, 2022). Developed nations such as Japan and the United States encounter less obstacles in terms of infrastructure due to their larger gross domestic product (GDP), while low-income countries suffer difficulties in this regard (Inbound Logistics, 2022; Pape, 2020). Multi-modal transport is seldom in Africa, which worsens the burden on road networks (African Development Bank, 2019). Inadequate coordination poses a significant obstacle to road repair endeavors, notwithstanding the allocation of funds for this purpose (African Development Bank, 2019). The road infrastructure in Kenya has been enhanced by government initiatives; yet, the effectiveness of supply chain planning and procurement still needs improvement (World Bank, 2017). Supply chain planning is essential for optimizing resource usage and achieving value. It directly affects the satisfaction of stakeholders (CIPS, 2012). According to the McKinsey Global Institute (2013), companies like Amazon showcase their competitive advantage by consistently delivering products on time. Kenya is currently seeing difficulties in road planning, which is having a negative impact on the development of its infrastructure ('Kigali Indoor Arena', 2019). Supply chain management (SCM) is the integration of operations management, with a strong reliance on technology (Chopra & Meindl, 2004). Security in business is contingent upon both internal and external elements, which are effectively controlled through the implementation of risk management strategies. These strategies encompass the process of planning, as outlined by Simchi-Levi et al. (2003). Supply chain planning (SCP) aims to minimize disruptions and optimize the coordination of resources (Zeng, 2003). Planning in road transport entails the synchronization of consumer demands with market availability by employing diverse procurement strategies (Chopra & Meindl, 2004). There are different ways to supply chain management (SCP), including demand-driven and production-driven models. Each approach has its own advantages and disadvantages, as discussed by Huang et al. (2009). Pull-driven plans prioritize resource optimization but may be inflexible, whereas push-driven plans anticipate needs but run the risk of resource wastage (Matebu et al., 2014). Gaining comprehension of these models facilitates the process of optimizing the supply chain.

Investments in global infrastructure, namely highways, have stimulated the development and progress of the construction industry (Tougwa, 2015). Construction in Kenya makes a substantial contribution to the country's GDP, in line with its national development objectives (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, 2018). The lack of adequate infrastructure, particularly in transportation and energy sectors, poses a significant obstacle to productivity and competitiveness in emerging nations (IFC, 2013). In order to maintain economic growth, the global community requires a significant amount of investment in infrastructure, which is projected to be around \$57 trillion between 2013 and 2030 according to McKinsey (2013). Poor road networks in Africa result in increased transport costs and impede economic growth (AfDB, 2013; World Bank, 2018). Infrastructure development is a top priority for governments worldwide, as it is crucial for the overall well-being of society and the promotion of economic growth (Orr & Kennedy, 2008; Howes & Robinson, 2005). Road transport is crucial in Kenya, and there have been significant institutional reforms focused on enhancing management and transparency, as documented by the Ministry of Transport in 2009 and the Ministry of Roads in 2011. With the increase in global infrastructure spending, it is essential to have efficient supply chain management in order to maximize public value and effectively use taxpayer resources (Sundqvist et al., 2014).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

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In Europe and other developed countries, the transportation of merchandise and passengers is mostly done by rail, accounting for 65% of the movement. This is followed by sea or water transportation at 20%, air transportation at 10%, and other forms of transportation at 5%. The European Union (EU) in 2018. By comparison, Africa, including Kenya, heavily depends on road transport, which accounts for approximately 70% of cargo and passenger movement. Rail transport contributes around 10-15%, while sea/water transport makes up about 5%. Air transport accounts for approximately 3%, and other modes of transportation contribute around 5% (African Development Bank [AfDB], 2018).

Research suggests that improving road infrastructure is crucial for Africa's economic progress, as it leads to reduced business costs, lower commodity prices, increased product competitiveness, and the facilitation of both domestic and international trade (AfDB, 2018). According to Accenture (2013), there is expected to be a significant increase in the need for road infrastructure in Africa, with investments estimated to surpass \$1.6 trillion in the next ten years. The importance of road infrastructure in promoting economic growth is emphasized in Kenya's national development goals, including Vision 2030 and the Big Four Agenda (Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure [MoT&I], 2018; Lutta, 2016; National Treasury [NT], 2015).

In spite of the grandiose goals set out in the Road Strategy 2000 (R2000) to build 1000 kilometers of new roads and maintain 34,000 kilometers yearly throughout Kenya, the actual results have been less successful, with just 650 kilometers of new roads constructed and 25,000 kilometers of maintenance performed per year. The disparity in performance can be ascribed to a range of variables, such as deceitful tactics in the management of the supply chain (Kenny & Musatova, 2011; World Bank, 2009; Luu & Chen, 2005). Furthermore, there is limited data that establishes a connection between public procurement policy reforms and enhanced road connectivity or increased trust in public supply chain management practices (MoT&I, 2018; Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act [PPADA], 2015; NT, 2015; Lutta, 2016). Academic literature presents contrasting viewpoints on the impact of supply chain planning practices on the operational effectiveness of government agencies in Kenya. Kariungu (2014) emphasizes the negative effects of complex supply chain management practices on the performance of major parastatals, specifically due to project delays. On the other hand, Apopa (2018) argues that government ministries' performance is greatly influenced by policies, collaborations, and supply chain practices. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between supply chain planning methods and the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya. Insights was drawn from multiple sources, including the AfDB (2018), EU (2018), NT (2015), and MoT&I (2018).

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The General and Specific objectives that guided the study were:

1.3.1 General Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study was to establish supply chain planning influence on performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya.

1.4 Scope of Study

The study delves into the influence of supply chain planning on the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya, encompassing both conceptual and contextual dimensions. Conducted within the premises of key road transport sector agencies in Kenya, namely KeNHA, KURA, and KeRRA, which are tasked with the nationwide facilitation of road networks, the research seeks to address the pressing need for enhanced market access for agricultural produce over the past decade. This necessity has prompted a consistent rise in public resource allocation toward improving road infrastructure. Despite substantial annual budgetary allocations and an apparent increase in donor funds directed towards road infrastructure development, taxpayers in Kenya have yet to witness a commensurate improvement in the robustness of road networks.

Procurement practices have emerged as a primary culprit behind the suboptimal performance of road transport sector agencies. The study unfolds over a period of 12 months, aiming to unravel the intricacies of supply chain planning within the road transport sector and its impact on operational efficacy and overall performance. By scrutinizing procurement processes, the research endeavors to shed light on the underlying factors hindering the realization of efficient and reliable road networks in Kenya

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

A theory is a generalization about a phenomenon, an explanation of how or why something occurs (Takač 2008). Theories describe, explain, predict, or control human phenomena in a variety of contexts. According to McMillan and Schumacher (2010), a theory is an explanation, a systematic account of relationships among phenomena. In this case theoretical framework, which was based on planning theory, examined phenomena through conceptual analysis and prior research (Camp, 2001). Planning theory emerged after World War II and focused on the public's interest in government intervention and its impact on urban development (Alexander, 2002). Planning, a practice that was observed since ancient times, required ethical deliberations, particularly with regards to the welfare of the general public (Howe, 1994). Supply chain planning coordinated actions to fulfill stakeholder requirements, which were essential for the achievement of corporate performance (Chopra, 2018). Supply chain planning in Sub-Saharan Africa was synonymous with procurement planning, which was mandated by law to ensure adherence to regulations (Howe, 1994). Insufficient public knowledge about procurement procedures resulted in legal disputes, emphasizing the importance of transparent planning (as stated in the Kenya Constitution, 2010). Supply chain planning was crucial in all sectors to optimize resources and establish confidence (Chopra, 2018). This study suggests that supply chain planning had a significant impact on the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya.

2.2 Conceptual framework

Turner et al., (2015) established a conceptual framework as the collection of distinct principles and concepts adapted from interconnected study disciplines and applied to constitute successive presentations

Figure. 1: Conceptual Framework; Source: Researcher (2023)

2.3. Review of Study Variables

Supply chain planning has been defined as sequencing of activities in a logical flow so that

implementation is tracked, monitored, and reported to ensure that allocated resources are utilised in an effective and economical manner thereby realising value for money (Chartered Institute of Purchasing and Supply [CIPS], 2012). It is more specific and important as a practice in supply chain management since it has direct impact on the delight of shareholders in any circumstance such as taxpayers in the public sector as well as investors in the private sector. Supply chain planning as part of supply chain planning is demonstrated in various forms but more predominantly through order fulfilment and on time deliveries, supply chain planning is a source of competitive advantage (Lysons & Farrington, 2012).

Part of the competitive advantage enjoyed by multinationals is continued on time deliveries such as that exercised by Amazon that specialises in e-commerce; this has been recently demonstrated by the start and completion of a 10,000-seater indoor arena in Kigali Rwanda in under 12 months through a Joint Venture between Rwandan government and a Turkish Investment Company, Summa (McKinsey Global Institute, 2013; “Kigali Indoor Arena”, 2019). Kenya is yet to witness a well-planned, started and fully completed road in the present and recent years as experienced in Tanzania and Rwanda; part of the reason to this is questionable supply chain planning which can become a real supply chain risk.

Supply chain planning is concerned with preparedness through alignment of events projected to be undertaken at a future date in a logical order catering for dependencies, interdependencies while avoiding overlaps that could become wastes in a process (Lysons & Farrington, 2012). In supply chain, the ordering of events in a chronological order minimises surprises within the supply chain thereby enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the supply chain performance (Chopra, 2018). By the very nature, supply chain which is the systematic throughput management of raw materials from source, through production, work-in-progress, finished products, warehouse, to consumption point (Huang et al, 2009).

Best practice requires that an organisation schedules the activities end-to-end, from requirements definition, call for tenders, evaluation, award of tender opportunity, contracting, contract management at implementation and project close out as part of delivery (Chiu & Lin, 2004). In the public sector such as road transport sector agencies, supply chain planning starts at budget allocation and ends at delivery and/ or disposal of the supply with a result of a supply chain plan otherwise called a procurement plan that becomes a public document (PPADA, 2015). The granular information on the particular planning activities target the length of time each of the stated activities takes and therefore being able to determine when the supplier is expected on site to deliver or better still, when the tax payer will use the road constructed, but it suffices to note that the timelines anchored in Law for public sector (PPADA, 2015). This study focuses on checking whether supply chain planning practice is and adheres to the Law.

Treating supply chain planning as with less importance is akin to failure planning be it is in private or public sector with organisation(s) in public sector having an ability to use supply chain planning to largely determine contentment of taxpayers to service delivery by its government and goes a long way in determining activities such as logistics for people, products, inspires the growth of development (and economy at large) of the county including the people’s livelihoods. In the private sector, supply chain planning as part of the larger supply chain planning, is so vital that organisations have invested in demand and supplying forecasting statistical models to neural networks including artificial intelligence to enhance data accuracy and enables organisation(s) to gain competitive advantage (Ciupan, 2014). Mwilu (2013) asserts that there is a correlation between supply chain planning and institutional performance as revealed by research on public research institutions in Kenya.

Recently, it was established by the National Treasury that in Kenya, County Governments’ poor funds uptake lead to over 60% of county governments returning allocated funds to the public

Research Bridge Publisher, International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research, Vol. 2, Issue 3, pp: (85-96), Month: September – December 2024, Available at: <https://researchbridgepublisher.com/> coffers for reason of not having spent which has been closely associated with delayed procurements due to sub-optimal supply chain planning (The National Treasury, 2015). This forms the basis for H_{01} : *Supply chain planning has no significant influence performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya.*

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study examined the influence of supply chain planning on the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya, considering both theoretical and practical elements. The study was carried out by the main organizations responsible for facilitating the nationwide road network (KeNHA, KURA, and KeRRA). The study utilized a cross-sectional approach, examining variations that occurred over a 12-month period. The research philosophy adhered to positivism in order to guarantee the collection of objective data. The target population included of 1500 personnel from the three agencies, who were selected via stratified random selection. A sample size of 254 was chosen to guarantee statistical validity. The collection of data was conducted using structured questionnaires and supplemented with information from secondary sources. Pilot testing was conducted to guarantee the validity and dependability. The quantitative data in this study were analyzed using SPSS, while the qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Correlation analysis and regression models were employed to evaluate the relationships between variables.

4.0 RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Response Rate

The total number of questionnaires distributed was 229. These questionnaires were self-administered to employees of road transport sector agencies in Kenya that is, KeNHA (Kenya National Highways Authority), KURA (Kenya Urban Roads Authority), and KeRRA (Kenya Rural Roads Authority). A total of 204 questionnaires were returned properly completed (Table 4.1). This represented an overall response rate of 89.08% (Table 4.1). According to Kothari (20015), a response rate of 50% is acceptable to analyse and publish, 60% is good, 70% is very good and beyond 80% is an excellent response rate. Saunders, et al., (2009) on the other hand indicate that 30 to 50 percent response rate is reasonable enough for statistical generalizations. Babbie and Benaquisto (2009) stated that a response rate of 50% is adequate while Bailey (1987) set an adequate response rate at 75%. Mugenda (2008) avers that a response rate of 50% is adequate, 60% and above good, and above 70% very good. Therefore, 89.08% response rate achieved in this study was excellent for subsequent data analysis.

Table 4.1 Response Rate

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Returned Questionnaire	204	89.08
Unreturned Questionnaire	25	10.92
Total	229	100

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics for Supply Chain Planning. Respondents were asked to state the extent to which they concurred to statement on the influence of supply chain planning on performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya. Five-point Likert scale statement questions were set for which the responses are presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Supply Chain Planning

Statements	Mean	Std. Deviation
Every fiscal year, supply chain management plans are developed and availed to all public members	4.9060	.29276
Supply chain plan is in place	4.6711	.48551
The supply chain plan is accurate	4.6577	.55473
The supply chain plan is up to date and inclusive	4.4765	.69344
In preparation of the supply chain plan, activities not undertaken in subsequent years are catered for	4.5235	.56454
Supply chain plan is available to members of the public including suppliers	4.6980	.54158
There is evidence that the public access the supply chain plans prepared	4.6913	.61402
Supply chain plan is an important tool in supply chain at our organization	4.4430	.60830

N= 204

The results in Table 4.1 show respondents' perceptions of several areas of supply chain planning within the analyzed firms. These findings are consistent with previous research, offering insights into the effectiveness and efficiency of supply chain planning practices.

The highest mean score of 4.9060 for the statement "Every fiscal year, supply chain management plans are developed and made available to all public members" emphasizes the importance of consistent and transparent communication in supply chain planning (Wang et al., 2020). This finding is consistent with the research, which highlights the importance of consistent planning cycles for organizational alignment and stakeholder involvement (Christopher, 2016).

Similarly, the high mean scores for statements such as "Supply chain plan is in place" (mean = 4.6711) and "Supply chain plan is available to members of the public, including suppliers" (mean = 4.6980) support the idea that transparency and accessibility are critical components of effective supply chain planning (Handfield et al., 2019). This is consistent with previous research emphasizing the importance of stakeholder involvement and information exchange in supply chain management (Lee and Klassen, 2008).

However, significantly lower mean scores for statements such as "The supply chain plan is accurate" (mean = 4.6577) and "The supply chain plan is up to date and inclusive" (mean = 4.4765) point to possible areas for improvement in supply chain planning processes. These findings are consistent with literature emphasizing the importance of accuracy, relevance, and inclusivity in supply chain planning to reduce risks and improve operational performance (Wagner & Bode, 2018).

Furthermore, the average score of 4.4430 for the statement "Supply chain plan is an important tool in supply chain at our organization" illustrates the perceived importance of supply chain planning in the researched organizations. This study emphasizes the importance of supply chain planning as a strategic enabler of business goals and objectives (Mentzer et al. 2001).

Overall, the results of Table 4.5 emphasize the need of frequent, transparent, and inclusive supply chain planning activities. Organizations can improve their supply chain resilience, responsiveness, and competitiveness in dynamic business contexts by addressing areas for improvement identified by respondents (Chopra & Meindl, 2016).

4.3 Inferential Analysis

4.3.1 Regression Model Summary

The study used multiple regression analysis to establish the linear statistical relationship between independent and dependent variables of this study.

H₀₁: Supply chain planning has no significant influence performance of road transport sector

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agencies in Kenya.

The objective of the study was aimed at examining the influence of supply chain planning on the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya. The literature that was reviewed in this study, along with the theoretical reasoning, suggested a strong influence of supply chain planning on the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya.

The model summary table provided valuable insights into the relationship between supply chain planning and the performance of the road transport sector. The high R-squared value of .732 indicated that approximately 73.2% of the variability in road transport sector performance could be explained by variations in supply chain planning. This indicated a strong and significant relationship between these variables, where effective supply chain planning had a positive influence on the performance of the road transport sector (Hair et al., 2017).

The adjusted R-squared value of .730, which was very close to the R-squared value, suggested that the model adequately adjusted for the number of predictors included. This adjustment was crucial as it ensured that the estimated model's performance was not overly optimistic, making it more reliable for predicting the performance of the road transport sector based on supply chain planning (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). The standard error of the estimate (.38196) represented the average distance that the observed values deviated from the regression line. A lower value indicated a better fit of the model to the data. In this context, the relatively low standard error suggested that the model provided a good fit to the observed data points, indicating the accuracy of the estimated regression equation in predicting road transport sector performance based on supply chain planning (Kutner et al., 2005). The Durbin-Watson statistic was 2.049, which was close to the ideal value of 2. This suggested that there was no significant autocorrelation in the model's residuals. This suggests that the residuals were independent of each other, which validated the reliability of the regression analysis results (Field, 2013). The findings from the model summary aligned with existing literature that emphasized the critical role of supply chain planning in enhancing organizational performance. Effective supply chain planning is often linked to improved operational efficiency, reduced costs, and increased customer satisfaction, all of which contribute to the overall performance of the road transport sector (Chopra & Meindl, 2016; Mentzer et al., 2001). This highlights the significance of strategic supply chain management practices in optimizing performance outcomes across different sectors, including the road transport industry (Wang et al., 2020; Handfield et al., 2019).

Table 4.3: Regression Analysis of the supply chain planning influence on performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya.

Model Summary ^b						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.855 ^a	.732	.730		.38196	2.049

a. Predictors: (Constant), Supply Chain planning
b. Dependent Variable: Performance of Road Transport Sector

4.3.2 Analysis of Variance for the supply chain planning influence on performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) table provided crucial insights into the relationship between supply chain planning and the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya. The significant F-statistic of 551.074 ($p < .000$) indicated that the regression model, which included supply chain planning as a predictor, explained a significant amount of variance in road transport sector performance. According to Hair et al. (2017), the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya was significantly influenced by supply chain planning.

The sum of squares for the regression model (80.399) represented the variability in road transport sector performance that was explained by supply chain planning. The value was significantly higher than the sum of squares for the residual error (29.471), suggesting that the variance in performance attributed to supply chain planning had statistical significance compared to the unexplained variance (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019).

The mean square for the regression model (80.399) represented the average variance explained by supply chain planning in predicting road transport sector performance. The value was considerably larger than the mean square for the residual error (.146), which further emphasized the substantial impact of supply chain planning on performance outcomes (Kutner et al., 2005).

Overall, the results from the ANOVA table indicated a strong and statistically significant relationship between supply chain planning and the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya. The findings in this study are consistent with previous research that highlighted the importance of efficient supply chain management practices in improving organizational performance and operational efficiency (Chopra & Meindl, 2016; Mentzer et al., 2001). Strategically aligning supply chain planning with organizational objectives allowed road transport sector agencies to optimize their performance outcomes and contribute to the overall development of Kenya's transportation infrastructure (Wang et al., 2020; Handfield et al., 2019).

Table 4.4: Analysis of Variance for the supply chain planning influence on performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	80.399	1	80.399	551.074	.000 ^b
	Residual	29.471	202	.146		
	Total	109.869	203			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Road Transport Sector
b. Predictors: (Constant), Supply Chain planning

4.3.3 Coefficients for the supply chain planning influence on performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya

The coefficients table provided crucial insights into the relationship between supply chain planning and the performance of the road transport sector. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for supply chain planning was 0.738, indicating that for every one-unit increase in supply chain planning, there was an associated increase of 0.738 units in the performance of the road transport sector. This indicated a strong positive linear relationship between supply chain planning and performance outcomes (Hair et al., 2017). The standardized coefficient (Beta) of 0.855 confirmed the strength and direction of the relationship between supply chain planning and road transport sector performance. The standardized coefficient enabled the comparison of the relative importance of different predictors in the model, revealing that supply chain planning had a significant impact on performance outcomes compared to other variables (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). The t-value of 23.475 was highly significant ($p < .000$), indicating that the relationship between supply chain planning and road transport sector performance was statistically significant. This indicates that the coefficient for supply chain planning was found to be significantly different from zero, which further emphasizes the importance of supply chain planning in influencing performance outcomes (Kutner et al., 2005). Overall, the results from the coefficients table highlight the important role that supply chain planning played in driving performance improvements within the road transport sector. The findings in this study are consistent with previous research that highlights the significance of implementing efficient supply chain management practices to improve organizational performance and operational efficiency (Chopra & Meindl, 2016; Mentzer et al., 2001). Prioritizing supply chain planning initiatives allowed road transport sector agencies to

Research Bridge Publisher, International Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research, Vol. 2, Issue 3, pp: (85-96), Month: September – December 2024, Available at: <https://researchbridgepublisher.com/> optimize their resource allocation, streamline their operations, and ultimately improve their overall performance (Wang et al., 2020; Handfield et al., 2019).

$$Y=1.235+0.738 \text{ Supply Chain planning}$$

Table 4.5: Coefficients for the supply chain planning influence on performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.235	.132		9.324	.000
	Supply Chain planning	.738	.031	.855	23.475	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance of Road Transport Sector

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.2 Conclusion of the Study

Through a comprehensive analysis, this study explored the influence of supply chain planning on the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya. With a response rate of 89.08%, the data collected was deemed reliable. Descriptive statistics indicated positive perceptions regarding various aspects of supply chain planning among respondents, highlighting its significance within organizations. The inferential analysis, including regression and ANOVA, revealed a strong and statistically significant relationship between supply chain planning and the performance of road transport sector agencies. The findings corroborated existing literature, emphasizing the critical role of effective supply chain planning in enhancing organizational performance and operational efficiency.

5.4 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are proposed; Firstly Road transport sector agencies should prioritize the development and implementation of comprehensive supply chain plans, ensuring accuracy, accessibility to the public, and alignment with organizational goals. Secondly, regular monitoring and evaluation of supply chain planning processes should be conducted to identify areas for improvement and ensure ongoing alignment with organizational objectives. Thirdly, all organizations should invest in training and development programs to enhance the skills and competencies of supply chain planning personnel, ensuring they are equipped to effectively execute their roles. Lastly, all institution should on foster collaboration and communication with stakeholders, including members of the public and suppliers, to ensure transparency and inclusivity in supply chain planning processes.

5.6 Areas for further Research

While this study focused on the influence of supply chain planning on the performance of road transport sector agencies in Kenya, there are several areas for further research on comparative studies to assess supply chain planning practices and their impact on performance across different sectors and regions. Also Should consider exploring the long-term effects of supply chain planning on organizational performance by conducting longitudinal studies over extended periods. In additional should consider supplementing quantitative findings with qualitative research to gain deeper insights into the factors influencing supply chain planning effectiveness and performance outcomes.

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